

The Effect of Solar Radiation in Open Steel Structures

Ivan Romo-Leroux^{*,a}

^aFluor B.V., Amsterdam, the Netherlands

* ivan.romo-leroux@fluor.com

ABSTRACT

Eurocode EN 1991-1-5 provides procedures to assess temperature changes in (closed) buildings, bridges, and also for structures which are in contact with process flows like industrial chimneys, pipelines, silos, tanks and cooling towers. However, the code does not address the temperature changes in open steel structures exposed to the ambient temperature and solar radiation.

This paper addresses this codification gap by considering thermal actions in open steel structures by assessing the maximum steel temperature considering the ambient temperature and the effects of solar radiation. The proposed procedure is based on the approach given for (closed) buildings by considering the inner temperature T_{in} equal to the maximum air shade temperature, thus $T_{in} = T_{max}$, and then following the approach of section 5 of EN 1991-1-5 with the outer temperature T_{out} as the maximum shade air temperature plus the effects of solar radiation $T_{out} = T_{max} + T_{3,4,5}$. The steel temperature T is approximately determined as the average of inner and outer temperature resulting in a steel temperature equal to $T = T_{max} + \frac{1}{2} T_{3,4,5}$ in open steel structures.

This proposed procedure is validated against the approach given to assess the temperature increase in unprotected steel exposed to fire using the heat transfer theory accounting convection and radiation effects as given in EN 1991-1-2 and EN 1993-1-2, and then compared against the approach given in section 6 of EN 1991-1-5 for steel bridges.

The contribution of this paper is to provide clarity when calculating the thermal actions in open steel structures which are generally present in industrial facilities and are currently subject to (mis)interpretations.

Keywords: Solar Radiation, Natural Convection, Heat Transfer, Thermal Expansion

1 INTRODUCTION

Outdoor steel structures without cladding are commonly used in industrial facilities. These open steel structures are exposed to the outside environment e.g. ambient air temperature and solar radiation. Eurocode EN1991-1-5 is used to define the thermal effects on (closed) buildings, bridges, industrial chimneys, pipelines, silos, tanks and cooling towers, however it does not explicitly cover the thermal effects on open steel structures. The maximum steel temperature for an outdoor steel structure is influenced by the maximum ambient air temperature as well as the additional temperature caused by the effects of solar radiation as shown in Fig 1.

This paper suggests a simple method to address the thermal actions on open/outdoor steel structures considering the convective heat transfer by the maximum air shade temperature by free/natural convection and the heat transfer effects by solar radiation.

Fig. 1. Heat transfer between the steel structure and external environment (air temperature and solar radiation) using an I-shaped steel beam as an example.

2 HEAT TRANSFER ON OPEN STEEL STRUCTURES

The main parameters that define the temperature in open steel structures are: the air temperature in the shade, the wind speed, and the effects of solar radiation which are influenced by the colour, finishing and orientation of the exposed surfaces.

The speed at which the heat is absorbed by the steel structure depends on the shape of the member, the section factor (ratio of surface area ratio volume) of the structural members.

To assess the temperature development in open steel structures exposed to the ambient temperature and solar radiation this paper uses the same heat transfer mechanism as per EN1991-1-2 for fire exposed surfaces. The temperature increase is given by the net heat flux \dot{h}_{net} [W/m²] considering heat transfer by convection and radiation.

$$\dot{h}_{net} = \dot{h}_{net,c} + \dot{h}_{net,r} \quad (1)$$

where,

\dot{h}_{net} is the net heat flux per unit surface area [W/m²],

$\dot{h}_{net,c}$ is the net convective heat flux component per unit surface area [W/m²],

$\dot{h}_{net,r}$ is the net radiative heat flux component per unit surface area [W/m²],

2.1 Heat Transfer by Convection

As per EN1991-1-2, the net convective heat flux component is determined by:

$$\dot{h}_{net,c} = \alpha_c \cdot (\Theta_g - \Theta_m) \quad (2)$$

where,

α_c is the coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/m²K],

Θ_g is the gas temperature in the vicinity of the (fire exposed) member [°C],

Θ_m is the surface temperature of the member [°C].

The gas temperature Θ_g is taken as the ambient air temperature for open steel structures not exposed to fire.

2.1.1 Heat Transfer Coefficient by Convection

At present, there is no unified formula for calculating the convective heat transfer coefficient. Generally, the expressions of the convective heat transfer coefficient include two parts: free convection and forced convection (1). Free convection is caused by the air movement due to the temperature difference between steel surface and the ambient temperature, while forced convection is mainly caused by wind. Some representative expressions of the free convective heat transfer coefficient for cases of low wind are listed in Table 1 followed by a graphical representation in Fig 2.

Table 1. Expressions of convective heat transfer coefficient α_c [W/m²K] for cases of low wind speed ($v \leq 5$ m/s).

Reference	Expression for α_c [W/m ² K] v is the wind speed in m/s	Limitations
(2) Duffie, 1980	$5.7 + 3.8v$	
(3) Liu, 2005	$2.5 + 4.2v$ (lower bound) $6.0 + 4.2v$ (upper bound)	
(4) Lee, 2012	$5.6 + 4.0v$ $7.2v^{0.78}$	for $v \leq 5$ m/s for $v > 5$ m/s
(5) Wei, 1989	(a) $6.31v^{0.656} + 3.25e^{-1.91v}$ (b) $4.35 + 3.0v$	for $v \leq 5$ m/s
(6) The Engineering ToolBox	$12.12 - 1.16v + 11.6v^{1/2}$	for $v \geq 2$ to 20m/s

Fig. 2. Coefficient of Free convection for wind speed $v \leq 5$ m/s from literature and Eurocode

For outdoor structures exposed to solar radiation the maximum steel temperature would be between the max air shade temperature and the temperature caused by solar radiation. When the

steel temperature is higher than the ambient temperature, then the ambient temperature has a cooling effect which is a favourable effect.

Fig. 2 shows a positive relationship between the coefficient of heat transfer by convection and the wind speed, since convection has a favourable effect then it is a conservative assumption to use a low convective heat transfer coefficient similar to the free/natural convection for cases of very low wind speed. The coefficient of heat transfer by convection as proposed by EN1991-1-2 with a value of $\alpha_c = 9$ [W/m²K] which is the average value for cases of very low wind speed ($v \leq 2$ m/s) can be deemed as a safe design assumption.

Note: For structures in the shade not exposed to solar radiation the maximum steel temperature may be consider as equal to the maximum air shade temperature.

2.2 Heat Transfer by Radiation

As per EN1991-1-2, the net radiative heat flux per unit surface area is determined by

$$\dot{h}_{net,r} = \Phi \cdot \varepsilon_m \cdot \varepsilon_f \cdot \sigma \cdot [(\Theta_r + 273)^4 - (\Theta_m + 273)^4] \quad (3)$$

where,

- Φ is the configuration factor, ($\Phi = 1,0$ may be used).
- ε_m is the surface emissivity of the member, ($\varepsilon_m = 0,8$ may be used).
- ε_f is the emissivity of the fire, ($\varepsilon_f = 1,0$ may be used).
- σ is the Stephan Boltzmann constant ($\sigma = 5,67 \cdot 10^{-8}$ W/m²K⁴)
- Θ_r is the effective radiation temperature of the fire environment [°C]
- Θ_m is the surface temperature of the member [°C]

For cases of open structures this paper considers that the effective radiation temperature Θ_r may be taken as the temperature T_{out} which includes the effects of solar radiation as shown in table 2.

Table 2. Temperature T_{out} for buildings above the ground level (from EN 1991-1-5)

Season	Significant factor	Temperature T_{out} [°C]	
		Surfaces oriented North-East	Surfaces oriented South-West or horizontal surfaces
Summer	0.5 for clear bright surface	$T_{max} + T_3$ ($T_3 = 0^\circ\text{C}$)	$T_{max} + T_3$ ($T_3 = 18^\circ\text{C}$)
	0.7 for light coloured surfaces	$T_{max} + T_4$ ($T_4 = 2^\circ\text{C}$)	$T_{max} + T_4$ ($T_4 = 30^\circ\text{C}$)
	0.9 for dark surfaces	$T_{max} + T_5$ ($T_5 = 4^\circ\text{C}$)	$T_{max} + T_5$ ($T_5 = 42^\circ\text{C}$)

As shown in Table 2 the radiation temperature strongly depends on the significant factor which is determined by its absorptivity (colour of the surface) as well as the orientation of the surface. At this moment there is not enough guidance in the Eurocode to select the appropriate significant factor which may lead to (mis)interpretations, therefore it is suggested to provide more detailed guidance in selecting the appropriate significant factor based on a range of colours as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Significant factor and range of colour (7)

Significant factor	Range of Colours
0.5 for clear bright surface	white smooth surfaces, grey to dark grey
0.7 for light coloured surfaces	Green, red and brown
0.9 for dark surfaces	dark brown to blue, and dark blue to black

Fig. 3a shows a map of Europe indicating the latitudes (45°N and 55°N) where the recommended values for T₃, T₄ and T₅ are applicable for regions according EN 1991-1-5.

Fig. 3b shows the variation of the solar radiation effects T₃, T₄ and T₅ for different building orientations.

Fig. 3a. Map of Europe showing latitudes between 45°N and 55°N.

Fig. 3b. Solar Radiation Effects T₃, T₄ and T₅ for different building orientations.

2.3 Temperature Development in Open Steel Structures

The maximum temperature in open steel structures exposed to the ambient temperature and solar radiation can be reached when the net heat flux \dot{h}_{net} [W/m²] is in balance. This means that the convective cooling down effect equals to the radiative heating up effect, so in the balance condition the net heat flux \dot{h}_{net} equals to zero.

$$\dot{h}_{net} = \dot{h}_{net,c} + \dot{h}_{net,r} = 0, \rightarrow \dot{h}_{net,r} = -\dot{h}_{net,c} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 4 shows the net heat flux for different steel temperatures. The maximum steel temperature at the balanced condition is at the intersection points where $\dot{h}_{net,r} = -\dot{h}_{net,c}$.

When $T_{max} = T_{in} = 50^\circ\text{C}$ and using $T_{3,4,5}$ for south-west or horizontal surfaces considering $T_3 = 18^\circ\text{C}$, then $T_{out} = 68^\circ\text{C}$, results in steel temperature $T = 58^\circ\text{C}$
 considering $T_4 = 30^\circ\text{C}$, then $T_{out} = 80^\circ\text{C}$, results in steel temperature $T = 64^\circ\text{C}$
 considering $T_5 = 42^\circ\text{C}$, then $T_{out} = 92^\circ\text{C}$, results in steel temperature $T = 70^\circ\text{C}$

Fig. 4. Net het flux, for $T_{max} = 50^\circ\text{C}$ in combination with maximum values for T_3 , T_4 and T_5

2.3.1 Time to reach target Steel Temperature

The time it takes the steel member to reach the target temperature depends on the section factor A_m/V and its shadow effect K_{sh} as indicated in eq. 4.25 of EN 1993-1-2. It can be seen in Fig 5a that lighter profiles heat up faster than heavier profiles.

The temperature development is asymptotic when approaching to the target temperature, therefore in order to account for any inaccuracy in the determination of the target temperature it has conservatively been assumed the time to reach 98% of the target temperature.

For example, a profile IPE 120 with a section factor $K_{sh} \cdot A_m/V = 0.70 \times 360 = 252\text{m}^{-1}$ it takes nearly 0.9hr to reach 98% of the target temperature, while for a profile HEB400 with a section factor $K_{sh} \cdot A_m/V = 0.65 \times 97 = 63\text{m}^{-1}$ it takes about 3.5 hours. Fig. 5b shows the temperature development for an average profile (e.g. HEA200) with a section factor $K_{sh} \cdot A_m/V = 0.62 \times 211 = 131\text{m}^{-1}$ where 98% of the maximum target steel temperature can be reached in about 1.7 hours.

The time needed to reach $T_{98\%}$ can approximately be expressed with the following equation:

$$T_{98\%} \approx \frac{226}{K_{sh} \cdot \frac{A_m}{V}} \quad (5)$$

where,

$T_{98\%}$ is the time in hours.

K_{sh} is the shadow effect.

A_m/V is the section factor in m^{-1}

Table 4. Time to reach 98% of the target temperature for different profile shapes.

Section	Shadow effect K_{sh}	Section factor A_m/V (m^{-1})	$K_{sh} \cdot A_m/V$ (m^{-1})	Time to reach $T_{98\%}$ (hr)
IPE120	0.70	360	252	0.90
IPE160	0.70	310	217	1.04
IPE200	0.70	270	189	1.19
HEA120	0.62	267	166	1.35
HEA160	0.62	234	145	1.55
HEA200	0.62	211	131	1.71
HEA260	0.62	171	106	2.13
HEA300	0.62	153	95	2.38
HEA360	0.64	128	82	2.74
HEB300	0.62	116	72	3.10
HEB360	0.64	102	65	3.42
HEB400	0.65	97	63	3.53

Fig. 5. Temperature development depending on the steel sections.

2.4 Proposed procedure for Open Steel Structures

The proposed procedure for open structures is adapted from the approach given for (closed) buildings by considering the inner temperature T_{in} as the maximum shade air temperature $T_{in} = T_{max}$. The outer temperature T_{out} as well as the average steel temperature follows the same approach as of section 5 of EN 1991-1-5 being the T_{out} as the maximum shade air temperature plus the effects of solar radiation $T_{out} = T_{max} + T_{3,4,5}$; since the convective and radiative effects have similar slope (rate of heat transfer), then the steel temperature T may be approximately determined as the average of inner ($T_{in} = T_{max}$) and outer environmental temperature ($T_{out} = T_{max} + T_{3,4,5}$) resulting in the following steel temperature equation.

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (T_{in} + T_{out}) \rightarrow T = T_{max} + \frac{1}{2} T_{3,4,5} \quad (6)$$

For $T_3 = 18^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow T = T_{max} + 9^\circ\text{C}$

For $T_4 = 30^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow T = T_{max} + 15^\circ\text{C}$

For $T_5 = 42^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow T = T_{max} + 21^\circ\text{C}$

2.5 Comparison with Type 1 Steel bridges

The proposed temperature development for open buildings is compared against the recommendation of EN 1991-1-5 for steel bridges (Type 1).

$$T_{e,max} = T_{max} + 16^\circ\text{C}, \quad \text{Temperature increase for steel bridges (Type 1)}$$

Fig. 6 shows a lot of similarities between these two approaches.

Fig. 6. Steel temperature for open steel structures versus Type 1 steel bridges.

3 RECOMMENDATIONS

The main recommendations proposed in this paper are additions/clarification to specific section of EN 1991-1-5:

- a) Add a note in Table 5.1 of EN 1991-1-5 indicating that for open steel structures the T_{in} may be assumed as T_{max} .
- b) Add a note indicating that for structures in the shade, which do not have a controlled environment and are not exposed to solar radiation, the steel temperature may be assumed equal to the maximum air shade temperature $T = T_{in} = T_{out} = T_{max}$.
- c) Add note in Table 5.2 of EN 1991-1-5 providing guidance on the range of colour for the appropriate selection of the significant factor.

4 REFERENCES

1. *Non-Uniform Temperature Fields and Effects of Steel Structures: Review and Outlook*. **Wucheng Xu, Deshen Chen and Hogliang Qian**. 5255, s.l. : Applied Sciences, 2020, Vol. 10.
2. *Solar Engineering of Thermal Processes*; . **Duffie, J.A., Beckman, W.A.** New York, NY : John Wiley and Sons Inc., 1980.
3. *Building Thermal Environment*. **Liu, N.X., Qin, Y.G.** Beijing, China : Tsinghua University Press, 2005.
4. *Investigation of Extreme Environmental Conditions and Design Thermal Gradients during Construction for Prestressed Concrete Bridge Girders*. **Lee, J.H.** 547-556, s.l. : J. Bridge Eng, 2012, Vol. 17.
5. *Research for temperature fields and temperature stresses of prestressed concrete single-box girder bridge*. **Wei, G.P.** 90-97, s.l. : J. Southwest Jiaotong Univ., 1989, Vol. 24.
6. **The Engineering ToolBox**. *www.EngineeringToolBox.com*. [Online] [Cited: 12 19, 2023.] https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/solar-radiation-absorbed-materials-d_1568.html.
7. **The Engineering ToolBox**. *www.EngineeringToolBox.com*. [Online] [Cited: 12 19, 2023.] https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/solar-radiation-absorbed-materials-d_1568.html.